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A STUDY OF TENSES USED IN ENGLISH ONLINE NEWS WEBSITE

Jittra Muta ^{*1}, Nutprapha K. Dennis ²

^{*1,2} English Department, Graduate School, Ubon Ratchathani Rajabhat University, THAILAND

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ABSTRACT

The purposes of this study were to analyze and describe English tenses used in an online news website and to examine which types of English tenses are frequently used in an online news website. The material in this study was 20 news in Mini-Lessons from Breaking News English L i s h . c o m. The research instrument was a checklist which determines and categorizes English tenses as past tense, present tense, and future tense. The data collections were analyzed with the frequency and percentage. The research findings of the study showed that all using of English tenses in the 20 news from the Mini-Lessons were 279 sentences; past tense were 155 sentences (56%), present tense were 120 sentences (43%), and future tense were 4 sentences (1%). The most English tenses aspect of the news were past simple tense and present tense; past simple tense, present simple tense, present perfect tense, and present progressive tense, respectively. In contrast, breaking news used the least English tenses aspect of the news was past perfect tense, future simple tense, past progressive tense, present perfect progressive tense, and future perfect tense, while there were no used past perfect progressive tense, future progressive tense, future perfect tense, and future perfect progressive tense in the 20 selected breaking news.

Keywords:

English news, Online English News Website, tenses.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In Thailand, English has been studied, but to be successful in English is actually very complex. Certain skills must be mastered if someone wants to achieve a high level of proficiency in English; listening, speaking, reading and writing. The learners can enhance their listening and speaking skills through conversation, debate, speech-making, role-playing and re-telling stories. Learners can write short stories, diaries and tell about unforgettable experiences to increase their writing skills. In order to increase reading skills, the learners should read graded reading texts. The learners must understand the meaning, the English grammar tenses of each word in context

and in a sentence to increase their ability in the English language. Reading is a great way of practicing English in their free time. The learners can take one word at a time at pace, without teacher peering over their shoulder.

Online Breaking News English Website is one of the main media that helps learners to understand English news and information, because it has various practices, activities and levels for the learners, which they can choose to study, to improve the use of the English language. The learners can also study many different kinds of sentences, for example past tense, present tense, and future tense. The learners can analyze the function and the kinds of sentences that are in the text. Learners often consider that it is a simple thing and it is not important to the learners. English teachers look at the meaning of the text and ignore or neglect the function and kind of the sentences. However, the kinds of sentences are important components in English learning because those are very useful for learners when they will express their utterances or write English sentences. One simple example is the difference of past tense, present tense, and future tense. Simply stated, past tense is past simple verbs, whereas present tense and future tense are not. Any grammar teacher, however, will tell students that the difference goes deeper than that: there are special rules for identifying and creating English grammar tenses, and these might take special studying to understand them completely, that students are still confused to distinguish about past tense, present tense, and future tense (www.english2days.com).

The data sources for this study were taken from articles on the online newspaper website “Breaking News English” (www.BreakingNewsEnglish.com) which covers topics from all around the world. This data were chosen because those articles contain many English nouns, but this site also increases our knowledge of what is happening now. Online newspapers are really popular nowadays, because the updating information is really quick. The information or the updating news will be posted on the site just in a few moments.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purposes of this study were to analyze and describe English tenses used in an online news website and to examine which types of English tenses are frequently used in an online news website

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The material of the study was taken from an Online Breaking News English Website (<http://www.breakingnewsenglish.com/>). There were 20 selected online news at Mini-Lessons to analyze. The study focused on three types of English grammar tenses; past tense, present tense, and future tense in twelve categories; *present simple tense, past simple tense, future simple tense, present progressive tense, past progressive tense, future progressive tense, present perfect tense, past perfect tense, future perfect tense, present perfect progressive tense, present past progressive tense, and future perfect progressive tense*. The selected news analyzed in this study consists of the breakdown of tenses used.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The findings from this study will be beneficial for Thai students who would like to learn English tenses by themselves using online news because there are many activities to learn such as interactive & printable English Lessons in seven levels and all skills to learn included. Moreover,

English teachers who would like to teach all skills using online news as their teaching resources. In addition, interested people or other language learners, educational institutions and practitioners to develop the use of the English language. Besides, it also guideline language policy markers for curriculum design.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

For the last part of literature review, there will be more close features of what other researchers have discovered in terms of English grammar, English grammatical structure, English usage, English Tenses, and typical characteristics of English usage.

Chausirisuksakul (2000) investigated 3 aspects of English grammatical skill, including noun phrases, verb phrases, and subject-verb agreement. The result of the study showed that the most problematic areas of the subjects' grammatical skill were subject-verb agreement, verb phrase, and noun phrase, respectively. The confidence on answer selection by subjects illustrated that Thai employees did not master a good level of grammatical skill. The findings of this study encouraged the future research and rethinking on grammatical skill and mastery of Thai employees in the business sector and conducted with surveyed data. The researcher can use this result to implement into the present study.

Meksujit (2002) conducted a study on grammatical structures used in the business sections of The Nation and the Bangkok Post. This study analyzes and compares grammatical structures. The result of the study showed that the structure clause(source)+clause(quote) was used most frequently in both newspapers while the structure clause(source)+that+clause(quote) was used the least frequently. Moreover, the sentences structures that have post modification occur most frequently whereas the structures: adverbial conjunction+clause+,+clause subordinate conjunction were used only 9.78%. Among four sentence types, complex sentences are most frequently used in both newspapers, followed by simple sentences, compound sentences, and compound-complex sentences respectively. The used of restrictive relative clauses occur more frequently than the usage of non-restrictive relative clauses in both The Nation and the Bangkok Post. In both newspapers, the omission of verb to be in the past participle is used most frequently with 77.46% whereas the omission of verb to be in the present participle is used 22.54%. Active voice is more popularly used in both newspapers than passive voice.

Phanphanich (1999) analyzed English usage in political news in English language newspapers. This purposes were studied the general characteristics of the language usage and analyzed pieces of political news in an English newspaper, Bangkok Post. The finding showed that sentence structures used the most was complex sentences and the least was compound-complex sentences. The omission of the verb to be used the most was past participle and adjective was used the least. The active voice sentence is frequently used in political news.

Somsilpa (2002) conducted a case study on typical characteristics of English usage in both domestic job advertisement and foreign job advertisement. This study analyzes English usage in 3 sections: layout and copywriting, choice of words and grammatical structures in sentences. The finding revealed that English usage between domestic job ads and foreign jobs ads imply some typical characteristics. In the layout and copywriting part, it is found that the layouts of foreign jobs ads are more complex and full of paragraphs. In contrast, the domestic ads contain lists. For

grammatical structures, sentences in domestic ads are quite simple and easy for readers, while foreign ads are more complex.

Surin (2005) focused on the use of English in cosmetic advertisement headlines and the samples were analyzed in three aspects: the vocabulary use, the grammatical structure and the types of headlines. The result showed that “nouns” were mostly employed in headline writing. Based on all word frequency, the study also indicated that the adjective “new” is the word that is most frequently used. There are five types of grammatical structures used. The two most popular types are “fragment” and “simple sentence” respectively. In respect to the types of headlines, direct benefit headlines are mostly found.

Suvarere (2006) focused on language use in airlines’ advertisements. Some major figures of speech and persuasive techniques of advertising claims found in 50 advertisements from 43 airlines are thoroughly examined. Besides the genre of airline advertisements, focusing on the move structure is also analyzed. The most frequently used figure is alliteration; the least used is simile. The trend of using figures showed that those related to sound repetition and without meaning change were more popular than those related to comparison and substitution, due to the former having less complexity and no need for interpretation. The claims offering some kinds of clear convincing evidence are employed more than those without, as this helps advertisements to be more believable. For the genre analysis of the airline ads, there are only four ads that contain all six moves in a sequenced order, so the move structure can be taught in a flexible way.

Wanithanachakorn (2005) focused on three processes, which are discourse structure, cohesion among the main parts and average article length in genre analysis of singers’ biography web pages: a case study. The lexical is the cohesive tie which is used the most frequent among the main parts, and the mean of total words per web page is 2310 words. From the results, it can be implied that the aim of singers’ Biography Web Pages is mainly to promote the latest albums of singers. The form of structure employed the most in Web Pages is time sequence.

Chodurová (2010) focuses on the analysis of the language of British newspaper in terms of distribution of tenses. The theoretical part introduces the English tense system, and its common use. Furthermore, it introduces conventions which are used for writing newspaper articles, including headlines. The analysis part concentrates on current British daily newspapers in printed version – The Daily Telegraph, and London Lite, and in electronic version – The Guardian, BBC News, and The Sun. The analysis compares differences between tenses used in broadsheets and tabloids, and also between printed and electronic version of newspapers. The results of the study showed that there are no perceptible differences neither between broadsheets and tabloids nor between printed and online newspapers. Their level is from the point of tenses comparable. The analysis has shown that the main change in the tenses is connected with the present tense, which is very universal tense and can be used partly for expressing the past, partly for the present, and also for the future.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study focused on analyzing context to twelve categories of English tenses; *present simple tense*, *past simple tense*, *future simple tense*, *present progressive tense*, *past progressive tense*,

future progressive tense, present perfect tense, past perfect tense, future perfect tense, present perfect progressive tense, present past progressive tense, and future perfect progressive tense usage toward online English news. The data from this study was quantitative and qualitative.

SETTING AND MATERIAL OF THE STUDY

The selected English news in this study was from Breaking News English Website (<http://www.breakingnewsenglish.com/>). The selected section for this study was twenty news as the world's breaking news from the 4th of December 2015 to the 30th January 2016 at Mini-Lessons. The researcher chose Breaking News English to study because the lessons are free, downloadable PDF format, classroom handouts are readily reproducible, interactive, and printable English lessons seven in levels from elementary to advance.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The research instrument in this study was a checklist which determines and categorizes English tenses; past tense, present tense, and future tense in twelve categories; *present simple tense, past simple tense, future simple tense, present continuous tense, past continuous tense, future continuous tense, present perfect tense, past perfect tense, future perfect tense, present perfect continuous tense, present past continuous tense, and future perfect continuous tense* from each news.

RESEARCH PROCEDURES

The procedures of data analysis of this study were; step 1: choose the website, step 2: select news from the website, step 3: analyze and describe the news by categorizing the sentences used in news writing into group according to the structure of tenses, which are divided into twelve sub-categories; *present simple tense, past simple tense, future simple tense, present continuous tense, past continuous tense, future continuous tense, present perfect tense, past perfect tense, future perfect tense, present perfect continuous tense, present past continuous tense, and future perfect continuous tens*, step 4: corrected the analyzed data by expert, step 5: categorize the analyzed data, step 6: analyze the percentage to get the frequencies of each sentence, step 7: make the conclusion and discussion.

DATA COLLECTION AND DATA ANALYSIS

Twenty online English news were collected from the selected website. With the number of sentence, the news selected in this study has sentence count approximately 279 sentences. The process to collect the data were; randomly select 20 English news from *B r e a k I n g N e w s E n g l i s h . c o m* at Mini-Lessons, collected and elicit English tenses from the 20 news then analyzed and checked by experts, adapted the 20 selected English news to make an e-book for the learners who would like to learn English grammar tenses by themselves. After the collected data was categorized, the researcher analyzed all the data in percentage to find out the frequency in each category and conclude the result with clear and concise explanation. The analysis process was conducted as an analytical description and reported in the narrative style.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of 20 selected breaking news English is summarized and presented by frequency and percentage of English tenses by summarized table only cover past tense, present tense, and

future tense; past simple tense, present simple tense, future simple tense, past progressive tense, present progressive tense, future progressive tense, past perfect tense, present perfect tense, future perfect tense, past perfect progressive tense, present perfect progressive tense, and future perfect progressive tense. The results showed that past simple tense and present simple tense were mostly found in the 20 selected news, while present progressive and present perfect were rarely used for the analysis of tenses. Past progressive, past perfect, present perfect progressive, and future simple were not much used in the 20 selected news whereas past perfect progressive, future progressive, future perfect, and future perfect progressive were not all found in the 20 selected news. All of the 20 selected online breaking news, there were 279 sentences with 8 of types all English tenses.

Past simple tense was used 151 of 279 sentences from the 20 selected breaking news, it was found in these news: 1) "Women do not get enough sleep" with 6 sentences; It is from a British group called the Sleep Apnoea Trust Association. 2) "Bananas in danger of becoming extinct" with 5 sentences; Scientists first discovered TP4 in Malaysia in 1990. 3) "Fairy tales could be 6,000 years old" with 7 sentences; Dr Tehrani studied the evolution of our early languages. 4) "Women have to pay more in shops" with 11 sentences; Researchers looked at hundreds of goods in the UK's biggest shops. 5) "Up to half of adults suffer from mental illness" with 7 sentences; Researchers questioned 5,000 adults about their experiences. 6) "New action to stop nuisance phone calls" with 4 sentences; The number of people who get monthly nuisance calls on their mobile phones increased from just over 50 percent in 2014 to 72 per cent today. 7) "Sugar could be harmful to our health" with 6 sentences; The tax was implemented on January 1, 2014. 8) "UN promises action on North Korea nuclear test" with 8 sentences; The USA said it does not think the test was a hydrogen bomb because the explosion was too small. 9) "Iran and Saudi Arabia in war of words" with 11 sentences; He was previously convicted of disobedience and of bearing arms. 10) "More people to stick to New Year's resolutions" with 7 sentences; Researchers in the USA asked people about their resolutions for 2016. 11) "Belgium arrests two over New Year terror plot" with 7 sentences; Police initially made six arrests but later released four without charge. 12) "Centuries-old diseases coming back" with 5 sentences; In 2013, it killed 1.5 million people worldwide, and that number is rising. 13) "School says Hello Kitty Christmas tree can stay" with 10 sentences; The tree was made from pink plastic and was adorned with Hello Kitty ornaments. 14) "Air France plane in bomb scare" with 12 sentences; There was a bomb scare on an Air France flight on Sunday. 15) "Consumers asked to throw away hoverboards" with 3 sentences; Electrical Safety First, a consumer protection group in the UK, said that around half-a-million people in the UK have bought a hoverboard as a Christmas gift. 16) "Ed Sheeran takes a year's break from social media" with 8 sentences; He apologised to his friends and family for his upcoming online absence. 17) "Scotland strips titles it gave to Donald Trump" with 6 sentences; He accused SNP leader Nicola Sturgeon of "failing to appreciate his greatness". 18) "Harmful bacteria getting stronger" with 9 sentences; Researchers looked into how antibiotics in food are making bugs stronger. 19) "Height may be the key to a happy marriage" with 11 sentences; Sohn said the appeal of a taller husband "gradually weakened over time". and 20) "Pet dogs lower stress in kids" with 8 sentences; Researchers looked at 643 children aged six and seven over an 18-month period.

Past progressive tense was used in only 2 of 279 sentences from the 1 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in "Air France plane in bomb scare"; The plane was flying from the Indian

Ocean island of Mauritius to Paris and the plane was carrying 459 passengers and 14 crew members.

The past perfect tense was used in 2 of 279 sentences from the 1 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in “School says Hello Kitty Christmas tree can stay”; A maths teacher at a high school in Maine, USA has been allowed to keep her pink Hello Kitty Christmas tree in her classroom and The teacher, Catherine Gordon, had earlier been ordered by the school principal Paul Butler to remove it after he decided it was an "inappropriate" Christmas decoration.

The present simple tense was used in 86 of 279 sentences from the 19 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in these news stories: 1) “Women do not get enough sleep” with 5 sentences; Apnoea is the temporary cessation of breathing, especially during sleep. 2) “Bananas in danger of becoming extinct” with 14 sentences; There is bad news for banana lovers. 3) “Fairy tales could be 6,000 years old” with 7 sentences; This is a time between the Stone Age and Iron Age. 4) “Women have to pay more in shops” with 2 sentences; Women have to pay a lot more in stores than men for almost the same things. 5) “Up to half of adults suffer from mental illness” with 5 sentences; Timely access to effective mental health treatment saves lives. 6) “New action to stop nuisance phone calls” with 9 sentences; Many people hate nuisance telephone calls. 7) “Sugar could be harmful to our health” with 4 sentences; Researchers say people might not even notice the changes. 8) “UN promises action on North Korea nuclear test” with 5 sentences; Japan wants the UN to act quickly to take action. 9) “Iran and Saudi Arabia in war of words” with 1 sentence; We deal with facts and criminal intent. 10) “More people to stick to New Year's resolutions” with 6 sentences; Many people make goals at the beginning of January but have given up by February. 11) “Belgium arrests two over New Year terror plot” with 3 sentences; The arrests are not linked to the November Paris attacks in which 130 people were killed. 12) “Centuries-old diseases coming back” with 5 sentences; Tuberculosis largely affects very poor people. 13) “School says Hello Kitty Christmas tree can stay” with 1 sentence; It just sucks the joy out of everything. 14) “Consumers asked to throw away hover boards” with 4 sentences; Hover boards cannot be used on public roads in Britain because they have not been registered as vehicles. 15) “Ed Sheeran takes a year's break from social media” with 1 sentence; The international superstar has 16 million followers on Twitter and another 5.5 million on Instagram. 16) “Scotland strips titles it gave to Donald Trump” with 3 sentences; Trump's mother is Scottish. 17) “Harmful bacteria getting stronger” with 4 sentences; The report is called the Review on Antimicrobial Resistance. 18) “Height may be the key to a happy marriage” with 1 sentence; A difference in height between the two partners could be a secret ingredient for marital bliss. and 19) “Pet dogs lower stress in kids” with 6 sentences; This compares with 21 per cent of children with no dogs.

Present progressive tense was used 11 of 279 sentences from the 7 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in these news: 1) “Bananas in danger of becoming extinct” with 1 sentence; A fungus called Tropical Race 4 (TP4) is killing millions of banana plants. 2) “New action to stop nuisance phone calls” with 2 sentences; Britain's government is thinking about taking action to stop these calls. 3) “Sugar could be harmful to our health” with 2 sentences; Governments in the United States and United Kingdom are waging a war on sugar in the interests of public health. 4) “Centuries-old diseases coming back” with 3 sentences; This is putting these old people in greater danger of getting TB. 5) “Air France plane in bomb scare” with 1 sentence; Five others

are being questioned by the police. 6) “Consumers asked to throw away hoverboards” with 1 sentence; Three of the UK's biggest retailers, including online giant Amazon, are advising customers to dispose of hoverboards amid safety concerns. and 7) “Harmful bacteria getting stronger” with 1 sentence; The researchers are calling for strict targets to reduce the number of antibiotics given to farm animals.

Present perfect tense was used in 22 of the 279 sentences from the 12 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in these news: 1) “Women do not get enough sleep” with 1 sentence; Health experts have warned that feeling exhausted due to a lack of sleep could be a sign of a serious underlying medical condition. 2) “Women have to pay more in shops” with 1 sentence; Other people have called it a "gender tax". 3) “Up to half of adults suffer from mental illness” with 1 sentence; Over 40 per cent of middle-aged women have been diagnosed with an illness at some point in their life. 4) “UN promises action on North Korea nuclear test” with 1 sentence; However, the UN has not said what action it would take against North Korea, nor when any measures would be put in place. 5) “Iran and Saudi Arabia in war of words” with 1 sentence; A war of words has broken out between Iran and Saudi Arabia following the execution of a religious figure by Saudi authorities on Saturday. 6) “Belgium arrests two over New Year terror plot” with 2 sentences; Brussels has been on high alert since those attacks, with intelligence reports suggesting an attack of some kind was coming. 7) “Centuries-old diseases coming back” with 2 sentences; The number of elderly who have to go without food has doubled in the past three years. 8) “Consumers asked to throw away hoverboards” with 4 sentences; They have asked manufacturers to address these safety issues. 9) “Ed Sheeran takes a year's break from social media” with 2 sentences; He has been active in keeping his fans up to date on his personal life but now wants to have a rest. 10) “Scotland strips titles it gave to Donald Trump” with 5 sentences; I have done so much for Scotland. 11) “Height may be the key to a happy marriage” with 2 sentences; Researchers have discovered what they believe is one of the keys to a happy marriage. and 12) “Pet dogs lower stress in kids” with 1 sentence; They have always known that a dog is great for helping a child's development and mental health.

Present perfect progressive tense was used only once 279 sentences from the 1 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in “Ed Sheeran takes a year's break from social media”; Sheeran has been touring the world since August 2014 giving dozens of sellout concerts.

Future simple tense was used only 3 of 279 sentences from the 3 of 20 selected breaking news, it was found in “Women do not get enough sleep”; It will come as no surprise to know that a lack of sleep isn't good for us., “Ed Sheeran takes a year's break from social media”; The singer will also use his time off to get surgery for a burst eardrum he got while doing a concert. “The research will come as no surprise to the parents of children who have a dog”.

According to the results of the study the English tenses aspects tested here, included past tense, present tense, and future tense, it was found that the most English grammar tenses aspect of the news of BreakingNewsEnglish.com was past simple tense, followed by present simple tense, present perfect tense, and present progressive tense, respectively. In contrast, it showed that breaking news used the least English tenses aspect of the news was past perfect tense, future simple tense, past progressive tense, present perfect progressive tense, and future perfect tense,

while there were no used past perfect progressive tense, future progressive tense, future perfect tense, and future perfect progressive tense in the 20 selected breaking news.

In conclusion, past simple tense and present simple tense were the most common English tenses in 20 breaking news, they were used more than all types, respectively. The results seem to support with Chodurová (2010) who studied on the analysis of the language of British newspaper in terms of distribution of tenses. The results of that study showed that there are no perceptible differences neither between broadsheets and tabloids nor between printed and online newspapers. Their level is from the point of tenses comparable. The analysis has shown that the main change in the tenses is connected with the present tense, which is very universal tense and can be used partly for expressing the past, partly for the present, and also for the future. These two studies had the same result, it could be explained that the mostly used tenses was simple tense. News language is a special language used for reporting the news. Its style has been formed for a very long time and nowadays has quite steady conventions how to write a newspaper article. As Huddleston (2008) claims that ‘the general term tense applies to a system where the basic or characteristic meaning of the terms is to locate the situation, or a part of it, at some point or period of time’.

4. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

This case study was analyzed and described in three types of English tenses used as past tense, present tense, and future tense and examines which types of tenses were frequently used in an online news website, with the title “Breaking News English Website” from the 4th of December 2015 to the 30th of January 2016 in total 20 selected news at Mini-Lessons. The researcher maintained the use of data analysis by apparently using the frequency and percentage of various types of tenses as a tool to use English language teaching most successfully. In the result of the twelve categories of tenses; past simple, past progressive, past perfect, past perfect progressive, present simple, present progressive, past perfect, past perfect progressive, future simple, future progressive, future perfect, and future perfect progressive to showed that simple forms were most frequently used in past simple tense and present simple tense and found that past simple tense was more popularly used than present simple tense. Comparing the frequencies of using English tenses; past tense, present tense, and future tense, those of past tense was 56% while present tense was 43%, and future tense was 1%. As regards of frequencies of occurrences in all types of English tense forms; for present tense, present simple tense (31%), present perfect tense (8%), and present progressive tense (4%), respectively. For past tense occur at significantly different as follow: past simple tense (54%), past progressive (1%), and past perfect (1%), respectively. Finally, future tense, there was only future simple tense (1%).

Based on all sentence frequencies, the study showed that past tense “past simple tense” was the sentence that was most frequently used 54%, the next ranks were “past progressive” and “past perfect” were used 1% for each tense. The second was present tense “present simple tense” was used 31%, followed by “present perfect tense” was used 8%, and the final rank was “present progressive” was used 4%. At the last rank was future tense “future simple tense” was used 1%.

The frequency of sentence category used for past tense, present tense, and future tense from 40 online news, “BreakingNewsEnglish.com” of 279 sentences used was as follows. The frequently

used past tense sentence totaled 155 sentences were 151 sentences of past simple tense, 2 sentences of past progressive tense, and 2 sentences of past perfect tense. The frequently used present tense sentence totaled 120 sentences; 86 sentences for present simple tense, 11 sentences for present progressive tense, 22 sentences for present perfect tense, and 1 sentence for present perfect progressive tense. Finally, the frequently used future tense sentences in 4 sentences were 3 sentences of future simple tense and 1 sentence of future perfect tense.

Absolutely, there are English tenses used in writing BreakingNewsEnglish.com which are differentiated according to the tropes on the purpose of the writer and situation; past tense was used most frequently were 151 sentences for past simple tense, while present tense was used the second frequently were 86 sentences for present simple tense and the least frequent was present tense and future tense, which were 1 sentence for present perfect progressive and future perfect tense.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings in this study benefit learners who are interested in English language and want clear sentences to use and understand, saving of time for planning and saving the money for learning English language through Breaking News English Website.

RECOMMENDATION FOR PRESENT STUDY

- 1) The analysis is useful for learners to increase understanding and permanent of memorize English tenses used in online news and enabling them to read online English news more easily without the pressure having a teacher behind him or her.
- 2) After the researcher conducted the study for teachers who would like to teach English tenses by using the product and online news can easily use this case study as their teaching resource to enhance learners' educational outcome intensively.
- 3) Other materials such as movies, songs, tales, newspapers, advertisements, etc., should be considered to study as well.
- 4) The scope of study could be broadened to include a larger amount of material of online news to get more details.

RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER STUDY

A study of English grammar; English tenses in breakingnewsenglish.com should studies English news of Mini-Lesson and should study English tenses used in news in other website such as VOA, BBC News, Bangkok Post, or News-The big project.

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